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Developing Innovative Interdisciplinary Engineering Education with IoT Technologies

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ABSTRACT

As we know, incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) into the Internet of Things (IoT) already revolutionizes the world with the capabilities of improving operational efficiency and helping avoid unplanned system downtime. Therefore, on the basis of the previous project (focusing on conducting project-oriented learning and using the application development training as a concrete embodiment of the interdisciplinary engineering education), the current project aims at achieving cultivation of creative thinking and conducts two representative trainings: (A) Proposing AI-powered application proposals with IoT technologies and (B) Implementing the proposed projects with embedded systems. Essentially there are four major steps involved in this project: (1) Do: developing applications of IoT, (2) Check: performing capture, storage, and data analysis, (3) Adjust: executing data-based learning, and (4) Plan: revealing insights that redefine the problem. On the topic of education training, we plan to arrange cross-presentation of creative thinking techniques and experience sharing in the field, which allows the students to leverage AI-powered IoT technologies. This paper presents the preliminary results of this project, which emphasizes on human-centric design process and aims to develop an architecture model for problem solving and application service. On the theme of creativity and design thinking workshops, several lectures and experience-sharing group discussions will be arranged. Related Topics cover: the technology and concept of creativity and design thinking, training procedures, tools, and the need and importance of creative thinking in engineering education. Hope that through this workshop activities and thoughts training, students can cultivate the ability to think creatively in engineering education.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the developments of networked sensing technologies, significant breakthroughs have been made for the Internet of Things (IoT) applications. In order to successfully implement the IoT applications, smart solutions linked to the cross-cutting issues will be an important subject in future engineering education. For achieving cultivation of creative thinking and the realization of interdisciplinary engineering education, two representative trainings are conducted: (A) Proposing human-centric application proposals with IoT techniques and (B) Implementing the proposed projects and assessing the system complexity. Fig. 1 shows the roadmap of the IoT technologies, which suggests that the ability to monitor and control remote objects is essential for IoT applications in the next three years.

On the basis of our current project, essentially there are four major steps involved: (1) Integrating creative and design thinking with local infrastructures and services (e.g., efficient parking space management, design of a smart environment), (2) Developing IoT applications (proposing a specific problem statement), (3) Embedded system implementations, and (4) Validating the system design via user feedback.

On the topic of education training, we plan to arrange cross-presentation of creative thinking techniques and experience sharing in the field, which may allow the students to leverage IoT techniques and describe general issues of people-oriented problems through observation and discussion. This paper will present the preliminary results of this project, which emphasizes on human-centric design process and aims to develop an architecture model for problem solving and application service.

Fig. 1. Roadmap: IoT technologies [1].

2. COMPLEXITY OF AN IOT SYSTEM

An important source of complexity within the IoT paradigm comes from the great amount of data collected. In most cases, the data also need to be processed in order to be converted into useful knowledge. Fig. 2 describes the basis of managing the complexities of an IoT system, such as domain expertise, sensing and networking, infrastructure, flexibility, and security [2]. Referring to [3], in view of the recent proposals on how to handle the complexity of Big Data, there are three general approaches to carry out the ensuing very intensive data processing: (A) local processing; (B) edge computing; and (C) cloud computing. Fig. 3 shows a schematic overview of these approaches for handling the complexity of the intensive data processing.

Fig. 2. The Complexities of a Managed Internet of Things System [2].

2.1. Local Processing.

This approach basically consists of processing the data where the data is collected. In this way, no raw data need to be communicated to remote servers. Instead, only the useful and relevant information is centralized to make smart decisions [4]. In addition, deploying the first level intelligence closer to the sensors produces an increase in the overall energy efficiency and significantly reduces the communication needs of many IoT applications, which develops the concept of ‘smart sensor’ with computing and communication capabilities. Nowadays, smart sensors are becoming integral parts of intelligent systems for the corresponding development of advanced applications.

Fig. 3. A schematic depiction of the approaches to handle the complexity of the intensive data processing (modified and reproduced from [3]).

2.2. Edge Computing.

Edge computing consists of the deployment of storage and computing capabilities at the ‘Edge’ of the Internet. The ‘Edge’ of the Internet can be defined as the portion of the network between sensors or data sources and cloud data centers [5]. The edge computing paradigm aims at deploying computing, storage, and network resources in this portion of the network such that lower end-to-end latency, high bandwidth, and low jitter to services can be achieved.

2.3. Computing.

The cloud computing technology gives the IoT applications the possibility to work in different environments in a very agile way using the same infrastructure [6], which favors the development of large-sized data centers where the resources are optimized through virtualization and efficient management systems. and an IoT system is considered as a service.

2.4. From the Design and Engineering Education Perspectives

As mentioned above, the system design can take several aspects into account, such as power consumption, communication networks, and the availability of computing platforms. Therefore, dynamic solutions can easily adapt to the more favorable approach to better handle the complexity and meet the operation constraints. The research lines in this field aim at reaching a smooth engagement with the IoT ecosystem, mainly by reducing the management complexity of dispersed edge resources and developing mechanisms to maintain the security perimeter for the data

and applications [7]. In this project, students are guided to explore the application design from engineering education perspectives.

Figure 4. A classical procedure for the discovery of knowledge based on data gathered from a large number of diverse devices [3].

3. CREATIVE AND DESIGN THINKING PROCESS

In Figure 4, a classical procedure of discovering knowledge from the data gathered from a large number of diverse devices is depicted. Our project explores the learning experience by integrating creative and design thinking with local infrastructures and services. Using the process of design thinking presented by Stanford (Fig. 5 (left)), learners can translate their observations into insights, products and applications that can improve human life. Note that although the thinking process of is human-centred, it is a system design viewpoint. Furthermore, the industrial mentor may be consulted to guide the learners from discovering problems, defining issues, proposing possible solutions, and finally finding the best solution by using the Double-Diamond Thinking mode (Fig. 5 (right)). It is to be hoped that through the idea of the concept of

creativity training, students can gain experience and skills for proposing general issues, which may provide a basis for defining specific problems (Empathy and Define). Then, through the combination of creative thinking training and engineering education, an appropriate solution may be explored to solve the problem (Ideate, Prototype, and Test).

(a) (b)
 Fig. 5. (a) Design thinking process [8] and (b) Double-diamond thinking model [9].

Fig. 6. A sociotechnical system designed in a complex environment [10]; the challenges of an IoT system design [11]

Therefore, on the basis of our previous project (focusing on conducting project-oriented learning and using the application development training as a concrete embodiment of the interdisciplinary engineering education), the current project aims at achieving cultivation of creative thinking (Fig. 6 (left)), where a sociotechnical system

is designed in a complex environment, and conducts two representative trainings: (A) Proposing application proposals with IoT technologies and (B) Implementing the proposed projects with embedded systems and exploring the design challenges of an IoT system, as depicted in Fig. 6 (right). Essentially there are four major components involved in an IoT system: (1) Physical System (Software/Hardware): developing applications of Internet of Things (proposing a specific problem statement), (2) Structure/Organization: performing capture, storage, and analysis of data (finding insights in data), (3) People/Social System: executing data-based learning (validating and modifying the system design via feedback), and (4) Task/Technical System: revealing insights that redefine the problem.

3.1 Application Proposals

On the theme of creativity and design thinking workshops, several lectures and experience-sharing group discussions will be arranged. Related Topics cover: the technology and concept of creativity and design thinking, training procedures, tools, and the need and importance of creative thinking in engineering education. Hope that through the activities and thoughts training, students can cultivate the ability to think creatively in engineering education. For instance, guide students to think about the intelligence and complexity in the design of IoT applications (Fig. 7), considering sensing and recognition, knowledge processing, decision and support, and learning, which may lead the students to consider the design issue from cross-domain perspectives and may further provide a better solution for the social service.

Fig. 7. The intelligence and complexity in the design of IoT [12].

3.2 Intelligent System Implementations

Under the architecture of an IoT application as shown in Fig. 7, we detail on I/O interface, interrupts and control mechanism, process operation w/wo OS, and data flow

and storage. In addition to setting up a development environment, students will conduct the labs on building a basic IoT device to sensing data, integrating multiple sensors and performing a complex sensing task, interacting IoT device with IoT gateway, processing data among IoT device, IoT gateway, and the sever end. Fig. 8 tracks the IoT applications and depicts possible wireless technologies for achieving smart cities. To validate the system design, the users as well as domain experts are invited to give suggestions on the ideas and the proposals based on student’s demonstration, which provides an opportunity for students to review their idea and proposals. The suggestion of the users, the degree of accomplishment, and the discussion among the students are helpful feedbacks to revise the content of the program.

Fig. 8. possible wireless technologies for achieving smart cities [13].

4. CASE STUDY

A course project is applied to develop a practical application using IoT technologies. The students are grouped into teams to discuss application architectures from cross-disciplinary perspectives and propose their problem statements, project deliverables, system descriptions, project setups, prototype implementation, test and feedback. Here, we use a smart parking system as an example to describe the design issues.

4.1 Problem Statement

This paper explores the system design and the efficiency of parking space allocation in urban environments, where drivers make their decisions by drawing on various levels of information about the parking demand (number of drivers), and perfect knowledge of the parking supply (capacity) and the applied fees on the parking facilities. Referring to [14], the questions that arise in this respect are as follows:

- How do different amounts of information on the parking demand affect drivers' parking choices?

- Could this be controlled by the parking service operator to minimize the cost that drivers incur and the redundant cruising cost?

4.2 Design Goal

Parking has become an important issue that many modern cities need to deal with. Studies show that, the average time to find a parking spot is varying from 6 to 14 minutes for major large cities in the world. Knowledge about travellers and their behaviour is the key to influencing mobility. Parking policy is one of the most effective forms of influencing mobility behaviour. Since exact knowledge about parking and mobility behaviour is lacking and effects of parking policy are difficult to calculate, existing research is not always well translated into usable knowledge for practitioners. Moreover, parking violation is also a big problem for city traffic. Many drivers tend to park their cars in prohibited areas, which can cause traffic jam and lead to car accidents. Therefore, the design of parking lot occupancy tracking system is an important issue. This case study focuses on using sensors (e.g., ultrasonic sensors, PIR human body infrared sensors), Lora devices and a web server to achieve real-time monitoring of the parking spots, which may help on reducing the time for drivers to find parking spots. Fig. 9 shows a typical parking detection system.

Fig. 9. The parking detection system.

4.3 Key Features and Contributions

In this case study, students explored parking space selection issue from strategic and psychological points of view. In the strategic method, they manipulated the costs and found out the optimum number of drivers in the competition. The studies show that the effect on total efficiency of system is significant and considerable. As shown in Fig. 10, by including drivers' personal characteristics in the type of decision making, the students managed to design a model which is much more efficient in information of available parking space. Possible scenarios are depicted in Fig. 11, where students may design a parking lot occupancy tracking system from inter- disciplinary perspectives for environmental monitoring, including parking detection, monitoring and

control, parking guidance, and parking payment, which are explored to demonstrate the project concept.

Fig. 10: Neighboring parking information (left) ; information of available parking space (right).

Fig. 11. A typical parking application with the IoT technologies [15].

5. CONCLUSION

This work presents the preliminary results of this project, which emphasizes on human-centric design process and aims to develop an architecture model for problem solving and application service. Hope that through the activities and thoughts training, students can cultivate the ability to think creatively in engineering education and think about the intelligence and complexity in the design of IoT applications. As shown in Fig. 12, top 3 skills in 2020 are “complex problem solving ability”, “critical thinking”, and “creativity”,

which are essential to handle the complexities of an IoT system and provide an example to echo with the conference theme: “Complexity is the new normality?”.

Top 10 skills

in 2020

1. Complex Problem Solving
2. Critical Thinking
3. Creativity
4. People Management
5. Coordinating with Others
6. Emotional Intelligence
7. Judgment and Decision Making
8. Service Orientation
9. Negotiation
10. Cognitive Flexibility

in 2015

1. Complex Problem Solving
2. Coordinating with Others
3. People Management
4. Critical Thinking
5. Negotiation
6. Quality Control
7. Service Orientation
8. Judgment and Decision Making
9. Active Listening
10. Creativity

Source: Future of Jobs Report, World Economic Forum

Fig.12. The top 10 skills you need to thrive in 2020 [16].

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